

Oligoquinane Hydrocarbons Display Dual Fluorescence & Phosphorescence Anti-Kasha Emissions

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Abstract

A series of molecules containing an oligoquinane structural motif have been prepared. These oligoquinanes are constructed by connecting azulene units through the five-membered rings, resulting in a ladder-type structure of azulene oligomers. These oligoquinanes form a sequence of oligofulvene units which endow them with cross-conjugated character. In addition, through the 1-position of the central azulene unit, one carbazole is appended. A complete synthesis, solid-state studies, which document the formation of porous solids, and spectroscopic experimental characterization are carried out. The optical properties are analyzed as a function of the temperature in steady-state mode and by transient absorption. The whole study is guided and comprehensively rationalized by quantum chemical calculations. The hybridization of azulene and carbazole into an oligoquinane backbone confers the dual capacity of anti-Kasha fluorescence (azulene-like) and intersystem crossing (carbazole-like), enabling the synergistic emergence of anti-Kasha phosphorescence at 80 K. The observation of anti-Kasha phosphorescence is particularly notable, given that these are nearly pure hydrocarbons, i.e., heavy-atom-free organic chromophores. Furthermore, the design of new chromophores disclosing fluorescence and phosphorescence dual emissions in anti-Kasha mode is very appealing in organic photonics. In general, the discovery of modes of inferring additional properties to actuate from high energy lying excited states is of special interest in fields such as photochemistry, catalysis and photovoltaics.

Introduction

Arguably, the major limitation of organic chromophores for their use in organic photonics is that all relevant photophysical processes are mediated by the lowest-energy excited state within a spin manifold. As a result, higher-lying excited states remain largely unexploited. This is known as the Kasha rule that states that molecules excited to higher electronic states rapidly relax via internal conversion (IC) to the lowest excited singlet state, S_1 . This is, all relevant photophysical and photochemical processes, i.e., light emission, exciton-to-charge conversion, stimulated emission, sensitization, chemical reactivity or photochemistry, are initiated from this lowest energy state.¹ There are, however, few reported examples where this rule is broken and the so-called anti-Kasha processes, or non-Kasha, i.e., occurring from high-energy excited states, merge as feasible, the most characteristic one being anti-Kasha light emission in the form of fluorescence.²⁻⁴ The challenge is twofold, not only to identify new examples of unusual anti-Kasha emitters, but also to make it with high-energy states able to perform specific photonic processes. The purpose implies fighting against a quantum chemical rule which tells us that electronic states are increasingly less spaced as the quantum numbers augment and smaller energy difference between consecutive excited states promotes more efficient IC, thereby suppressing the possibility for a high-energy excited state to follow a relaxation pathway different than IC.⁵ Along these lines, an improved molecule for photonic applications should have one or several high-energy excited states able to avoid IC and develop enriching photophysical events, such as luminescence, photochemistry and intersystem crossing (ISC). ISC, a process where singlets transform into triplets, is very valuable for several reasons such as triplet-mediated photochemical reactions and triplet emission

in the form of phosphorescence. There are a few reports of anti-Kasha phosphorescence in the current literature,⁶⁻⁸ which are all mediated by the presence of heavy-atoms that are needed to promote ISC. However, the use of heavy atoms is certainly not desired in the large-scale deployment. In this scenario, the development of heavy-atom free hydrocarbon molecules able to produce ISC, the design of anti-Kasha emitters and anti-Kasha phosphorescence (non-allowed triplet-singlet emission) all together represent a triple challenge for the current research of chromophores in the area of organic photonics.

Among hydrocarbon compounds, azulene comprises the benchmark example for anti-Kasha emission, wherein large difference between the S_2 and S_1 energy levels, owing to distinctive aromatic properties of these states, hinders fast IC to S_1 . This lack of IC results in a larger lifetime of the azulene S_2 state, which enables it to decay with photon emission activity.^{9,10} The main photophysical properties of azulene are a main absorbance band ($S_0 \rightarrow S_2$) at 350 nm and the lowest energy forbidden absorption ($S_0 \rightarrow S_1$) around 600 nm and fluorescent emission at 400 nm ($S_2 \rightarrow S_0$) with very low (< 1%) fluorescence quantum yield.¹¹⁻¹³ Unfortunately, despite many efforts trying to modify the structure of azulene, these have not been translated into substantial changes on their photophysical action. Different attempts and substrates have been approached to discover new anti-Kasha chromophores with more versatility, such as molecules with delayed population of the higher-energy excited states¹⁴ using radicals¹⁵ and diradicals,¹⁶ or using solid samples.^{10,17}

π -Conjugated oligomers and polymers in organic electronics have been conceived, either with trans-, cis- or cis-trans conjugation of consecutive double bonds, all displaying linear π -conjugation (Scheme 1), which is the main tuning tool of electronic properties. Furthermore, these conjugated systems have been primarily constructed with alternant aromatic monomers. In general, this linear π -conjugation in aromatic units suitcases the situation of minimally effective ISC (i.e., at least up to the point of producing phosphorescence) on chromophores following the Kasha rule. To overcome these restrictions, the preparation of π -conjugated oligomers featuring patterns of cross-conjugation and made with non-aromatic/non-alternant units is attractive, but with very limited casuistry (i.e., linearly connected oligoazulenes is an example).¹⁸ In this scenario, we devise the preparation of new oligomers with four fundamental novel aspects: i) representing ladder-type oligoazulene (consecutive azulene units are joint through two single CC bonds) provoking the rigidification of the oligomer structure;¹⁹ ii) embedding an oligomer sequence of fulvene units or oligofulvenes,^{20,21} which induces cross-conjugation; iii) being mainly formed by non-alternant odd-member rings (i.e., five or seven); and iv) constituting a skeleton with oligoquinane²² motif (array of fused five-members rings), which is rather uncommon in the field. We posit that the conjunction of all these distinctive electronic components will produce new systems with unexpected new optical and photophysical features.

Herein, we present a set of three novel molecules where carbazole and azulene have been hybridized, by attachment at the 1-position of carbazole to the 2-position of azulene, to take advantage of the properties of both moieties. The azulene fragment forms a central oligoquinane structure with fused five-membered rings arranged in a ladder-type oligoazulene to produce anti-Kasha emission.^{23,24}

Whereas the presence of carbazole moiety might boost ISC in such a way that the combination of the two might give rise to an unexpected property of anti-Kasha phosphorescence in heavy-atom-free molecules. Now, we report that the discovery of anti-Kasha phosphorescence emission in nearly pure hydrocarbons is a breakthrough in the field with new possibilities in applications of high energy photoswitches,^{25,26} photocatalysis^{5,27,28} and photovoltaics.^{29,30} Furthermore, the fabrication of new chromophores showcasing dual emission combining fluorescence and phosphorescence is significantly appealing for a wide field of emission applications such as lasers^{31,32} or LEDs.^{33,34}

Results and Discussion

Synthesis and Solid-State Characterization. The synthetic route is depicted in Scheme 2. Buchwald-Hartwig amination of 2-chloroazulene (**azu-Cl**) with commercially available 3,6-di-*tert*-butyl-9H-carbazole efficiently provided **NB0A1** in 83% yield. Iodination of **NB0A1** using NIS afforded compound **1** in 93% yield. Subsequently, Suzuki-Miyaura coupling of **1** with either (2-bromophenyl)boronic acid or 2-(4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)azulene yielded compounds **2** (42%) and **3** (46%), respectively. Direct intramolecular arylation of **2** under palladium catalysis afforded the target compound **NB2A1** in 40% yield. Alternatively, chlorination of **3** with NCS gave compound **4** (67%), which underwent direct arylation to furnish the target compound **NB0A3** in 18% yield. The structures of **NB2A1** and **NB0A3** were confirmed by HR-MS, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, and single-crystal X-ray diffraction analysis.

Single crystals of **NB2A1** and **NB0A3** were grown by slow evaporation of methanol into a toluene solution (for **NB2A1**) and vapor diffusion of hexane into a carbon disulfide solution (for **NB0A3**), respectively. As shown in Fig. 1a and 1b, both compounds adopt structures featuring two nearly planar segments, which intersect along the axis connecting the carbazole group and the five-membered ring A, with torsional angles of 49.2° and 42.0°, respectively. The molecular dimensions across the oligoquinane-containing planes measure 10.6 Å (**NB2A1**) and 14.8 Å (**NB0A3**). Notably, both structures exhibit shortened transannular bonds (ring A to ring B) of approximately 1.38 Å (Fig. 1a,b), diverging significantly from the typical bond length of 1.48 Å in classical azulene. Molecular stacking analysis (Fig. 1c,d) reveals distinct packing motifs. **NB2A1** crystallizes with hollow circular channels (diameter: 7.4 Å) aligned along the *c*-axis (Fig. 1c). These channels, formed by three symmetry-related molecules constituting the fundamental repeat unit, arrange into equilateral triangles. Adjacent triangular units interconnect, generating extended noncovalent porous frameworks. In contrast, **NB0A3** exhibits a more conventional packing structure (Fig. 1d), where four symmetry-independent molecules form the lattice unit. This arrangement features intermolecular π - π stacking (≈ 3.4 Å) between pentaquinane-containing units and C-H $\cdots\pi$ interactions (≈ 2.7 Å) involving carbazole units and adjacent pentaquinane-containing molecular moieties (Fig. 1d). These interactions assemble the molecules into discrete 1D columns.

Absorption properties. Figure 2 shows the absorbance spectra for **NB2A1** in 2-methyltetrahydrofuran and their dependence with temperature (**NB0A1** and **NB0A3** are shown in Fig. S1). In all cases, a medium intensity band is present (at 428, 487 and 452 nm for **NB0A1**, **NB2A1** and **NB0A3**, respectively) at 298 K. Interestingly, **NB0A1** and **NB2A1** show a very intense band at 332 and 303 nm, respectively, which has no

correspondence in **NB0A3**. In general, upon cooling down the solutions, the absorption spectra became: i) more resolved and ii) the 400–500 nm medium intense bands red-shifted. However, there were significant differences between **NB0A3** and **NB0A1/NB2A1**. On one hand, in **NB0A1/NB2A1**, the 400–500 nm wide bands at 298 K split at 80 K into a more intense narrower band and a new vibronic band. However, **NB0A3** shows no major differences in the spectral shape and no new bands appear on cooling. The frozen solution restricts vibrational motions associated with freely rotating single bonds, consequently, the main spectral changes in these conditions should arise from structure modifications around the C-N single bond linking the carbazole and central azulene fragments. The significant changes with cooling in the spectra of **NB0A1** and **NB2A1** concerning the 400–500 nm band suggest that this transition involves electronic coupling between the carbazole and azulene-containing fragments. In addition, the lack of thermal changes in **NB0A3** 458 nm band indicates a weaker electronic interaction between the two subunits.

To further interpret the experimental absorption spectra, we performed time-dependent density functional theory (TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d)) calculations (see “Exchange-correlation functional benchmark” section in the Supporting Information). The low-lying singlet excitations for **NB2A1** are summarized in Fig. 2 together with a comparison between the experimental and simulated spectra (data corresponding to **NB0A1** and **NB0A3** is in Supplementary Fig.S2). In the three molecules, very low oscillator strength transitions are predicted for excitations at low energies, in good agreement with the very weak experimental bands observed in this region. Specifically, for **NB2A1**, these low-energy bands are experimentally present at 613 and 680 nm, which correspond to the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ and $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transitions, respectively. The low oscillator strength indicates the forbidden nature of these low-energy transitions, in line with other azulene derivatives discussed in the literature.^{35,36} In contrast, an intense absorption experimental band at ~ 300 nm, calculated at 312 nm, in **NB2A1** is observed and assigned to the $S_0 \rightarrow S_5$ transition from TDDFT calculations. This state owes to a mixture of HOMO-3 \rightarrow LUMO and HOMO \rightarrow LUMO + 3 transitions, therefore involving orbitals with large contributions from azulene-based orbitals (as seen in Supplementary Information, Fig. S3). Finally, there is an accumulation of transitions in the 250–300 nm interval, which disclose increasing oscillator strengths when moving to higher excitation energies, from the $S_0 \rightarrow S_6$ to $S_0 \rightarrow S_{15}$.

The analysis of the medium-intensity absorption band displayed more differences between **NB0A3** and the other two molecules. For **NB2A1**, this absorption band is observed at 497 nm and assigned to the $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ theoretical transition at 391 nm, which primarily corresponds to a HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO excitation (details in the Supplementary Information, Tables S2 and S3). Notably, both of these orbitals exhibit substantial delocalization over the carbazole and azulene moieties, justifying its sensitivity to temperature, as seen in Fig. 2. The critical role of the carbazole unit in the origin of the experimental 497 nm band in **NB2A1** is further confirmed by TDDFT calculations on a truncated structure lacking the carbazole fragment (see Supplementary Fig. S6), where no electronic transition with appreciable oscillator strength appears in the 400–500 nm region. Conversely, in **NB0A3** another medium-intensity absorption band in the same interval is detected at 458 nm which, however, corresponded to a different

excitation, the HOMO-1 → LUMO + 2 transition, whose orbitals are now mainly localized over the oligoquinane-conjugated azulenic moiety (i.e., they are independent of the carbazole).²²

Emission properties. Figure 3 shows the absorption/excitation/emission of the three molecules at 298 and 80 K, all of which display fluorescent emission with distinct characteristics. Excitation to the low-energy bands (in the 400–500 nm region), associated with the $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ and $S_0 \rightarrow S_4$ transitions of **NB2A1** and **NB0A1** respectively, shows no emissions. However, **NB2A1** shows an intense emission band centered at 353 nm at 298 K upon exciting at 300 nm on the calculated $S_0 \rightarrow S_5$ excitation band. Notably, this deexcitation appears at higher energy than the previously assigned $S_0 \rightarrow S_1/S_4$ absorptions, confirming its anti-Kasha nature. This is further consistent with the assignment of the 303 nm band to an azulenic transition and aligns with the anti-Kasha emissions reported for other azulene derivatives.^{37,38} The measured emission lifetime of the **NB2A1** band at 353 nm at 298 K is 2.1 ns, which clearly identifies it as a fluorescent emission (Supplementary Fig.S7). **NB0A1** shows similar behavior than **NB2A1**, with an anti-Kasha azulenic emission at 290 nm at 298 K. **NB0A3**, however, shows negligible fluorescence.

The photophysical discussion of the three molecules is much richer in cryogenic conditions. At 80 K, new emission bands appeared for **NB0A1** and **NB2A1** peaking at 415 and 422 nm, respectively, whereas no emission bands appeared for **NB0A3**. In the case of **NB2A1**, this low temperature new band at 422 nm co-exists with another one at 347 nm, which is correlated with the fluorescence band at 353 nm at 298 K (i.e., the blueshift 353 → 347 nm is a consequence of the frozen molecular structure at 80 K). Interestingly, the lifetime of the new appearing band at 422 nm is orders of magnitude larger than the lifetime previously discussed at 298 K for the anti-Kasha fluorescence of **NB2A1** (2.1 ns). These new bands, which appeared at 80 K, had lifetimes of 730 and 800 μ s (Supplementary Fig.S8) for **NB0A1** and **NB2A1**, respectively, suggesting that these emissive bands likely originate from triplet-state emissions, i.e., phosphorescence. This assignment is in line with a markedly red-shift relative to the observed anti-Kasha fluorescence emission (i.e., due to exchange energy between singlets and triplets). Interestingly, in both cases, this phosphorescence occurs at larger energies than the lowest-energy absorptions (namely S_1). This phosphorescence at larger energy than S_1 indicates its origin from a T_n , where $n > 1$, since T_1 is expected to be lower in energy than S_1 (by Hund's rule). In consequence, these results indicate that the observed emission in **NB0A1** and **NB2A1** originates from anti-Kasha phosphorescence.

Transient Absorption Spectroscopy. To further explore the photophysical properties of these molecules, we conducted femtosecond transient absorption spectroscopy (fs-TAS) in 2-MeTHF solution at 298 K (Fig. 3). Upon excitation of **NB0A3** at 450 nm, we find out a featureless excited state absorption (ESA) band at 600–650 nm, which narrows upon 0.2 ps along with a negative large intensity signal due to the ground state bleaching absorbance at 515 nm. This initial band decays in favor of a multiband ESA feature with maxima at 550, 600 and 650 nm. We have seen previously similar transient absorption spectral features in other azulene derivatives,^{39–41} where species with similar ESA spectral shape were generated in similar experiments and assigned to absorptions from higher energy singlet excited states, S_n ($n > 1$). In addition, this correlation is further supported by the similarity in the excited state dynamics

seen exciting **NB0A3** at 449 nm in comparison to other azulenic compounds upon excitation at their azulenic bands, what is again coherent with the proposed azulenic character assignment of this **NB0A3** band.

Excitation of **NB2A1** at 300 nm produces, at very short times, an ESA band at 460 nm that extends up to 750 nm and decays in 1 ps to give rise to an ESA band at 525 nm with a lifetime of 10 ps. This excited state band at 525 nm shares a very similar kinetics with the negative signal at 487 nm, which matches the absorbance band, and hence, can be assigned to the ground state bleaching. In addition, at longer time scales it is possible to detect a low-intensity ESA feature in the 600–650 range that outlives the equipment detection limit time, around 5 ns, which is not present when excited at 485 nm (Supplementary Fig. S9). To unequivocally assign this long-lived species, we performed microsecond transient absorption spectroscopy (μ s-TAS) shown in Supplementary Fig. S10. Upon excitation of **NB2A1** at 300 nm on μ s-TAS, we find out a broad band centered at 600 nm that lives over 10 μ s, which matches with the feature seen at 1 ns in the ps-TAS (Fig. 3). This band completely disappears upon flushing the solution with oxygen, and it is completely recovered when saturated back with nitrogen (Supplementary Fig. S10). This latter experiment confirms the assignment of this band to the formation of triplets in **NB2A1**. The presence of these triplets upon excitation of **NB2A1** at 300 nm at 298 K is in accordance with the steady-state phosphorescence described in the emission discussion at 80 K. On the other hand, μ s-TAS measurements of **NB0A3** yielded negligible signals (Supplementary Fig. S11), consistent with the absence of long-lived excited species for this compound.

Theoretical characterization of anti-Kasha emissions. To investigate the origin and nature of anti-Kasha emissions, we carried out additional quantum chemical calculations. In particular, we focused on a detailed computational analysis of the photoinduced decay pathways in **NB2A1**, as this molecule displays both high-energy singlet and triplet emissions. Our efforts specifically target the characterization of the excited states responsible for the anti-Kasha fluorescence and phosphorescence observed upon 300 nm excitation, as well as the identification of the ISC mechanisms that enable population of the triplet manifold followed by photon emission. All these mechanisms are summarized in the Jablonski diagram in Fig. 4.

At CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory, the $S_0 \rightarrow S_5$ excitation is identified as the primary contributor to the 300 nm absorption band of **NB2A1**, with a computed excitation energy of 3.97 eV (312 nm) and a significant oscillator strength ($f = 0.138$). Geometry optimization on the S_5 potential energy surface results in a relaxed vertical emission energy of 3.81 eV (326 nm), while maintaining strong optical activity ($f = 0.123$). These findings are in excellent agreement with the experimentally observed high-energy fluorescence band at 354/346 nm (Fig. 3b), supporting the assignment of the S_5 state as the origin of the anti-Kasha fluorescence in **NB2A1**. The radiative decay from this state involves a hole-electron recombination process in which the hole is predominantly localized on the carbazole unit (HOMO-3 in Fig. 4), whereas the electron is delocalized across both the carbazole and the azulene-derived moieties (LUMO in Fig. 4). This electronic configuration indicates that the emission carries substantial electron recombination character from carbazole to azulene.

To elucidate the generation of triplet states observed upon photoexcitation of **NB2A1** at 300 nm under low-temperature conditions, we conducted a computational investigation of potential ISC pathways, considering the initial population of the S_5 state. At the ground-state geometry, the bright S_5 state is nearly degenerate with the dark ($f < 10^{-3}$) S_6 state, with a computed energy gap of approximately 30 meV. This small gap suggests efficient non-radiative back and forth IC between S_6 and S_5 . The energy gap between S_5 and S_4 is considerably larger (~ 460 meV) and is the reason for the detection of anti-Kasha fluorescence, though IC to S_4 may still represent a competitive decay pathway. In contrast, we exclude S_3 as a precursor for ISC, since it is experimentally associated with absorption at lower energy (~ 487 nm) than the observed anti-Kasha triplet emission (centered at 421 nm). Based on these considerations, we propose that following photoexcitation to S_5 , the molecule undergoes rapid IC and relaxation on the PESs of S_4 - S_6 . ISC is then expected to occur from the minima of these excited singlet states (see Fig. 4 and Table S5, which summarizes the computed singlet-triplet energy gaps and spin-orbit coupling constants (SOCCs) between the relaxed S_4 - S_6 states and nearby triplet states). The results highlight $S_5 \rightarrow T_{10}$ and $S_6 \rightarrow T_8$ as the most efficient ISC channels within this manifold, due to their small energy gaps and relatively large SOCCs in the order of 1 cm^{-1} .

Therefore, ISC from the anti-Kasha singlet S_5 (or alternatively from the nearby singlets S_4 and S_6) initially populates high-lying triplet states within the T_6 - T_{12} range. At these energies, electronic structure calculations reveal a dense manifold of triplet states, which is expected to facilitate rapid and consecutive IC steps. Notably, this cascade appears to slow significantly at the T_4 state, which is separated from T_3 by a relatively large energy gap (~ 0.8 eV, Table S4). According to the energy gap law, such a separation may hinder further IC to lower triplets. Optimization on the T_4 potential energy surface yields an energy minimum with a vertical de-excitation energy to the ground state of 2.67 eV (464 nm), which aligns well with the experimentally observed long-lived emission band centered at 421 nm at 80 K. These results support the assignment of the anti-Kasha phosphorescent emission to radiative decay from the T_4 state, which involves a singly occupied molecular orbital delocalized over both the carbazole and azulene units, and an unpaired electron residing in a π -orbital primarily localized on the azulene derivative (Fig. 4). Along these lines, the mixed azulene-carbazole character of these excitations make plausible the ISC channels to the triplet manifold as well as the subsequent additional triplet-singlet conversion during phosphorescence. Indeed, given the absence of carbazole content in the potential ISC channels between high-energy excited states of **NB0A3**, phosphorescence is absent due to the azulene composition of such transitions.

Conclusions

In the search of new π -conjugated structures based on non-alternant, non-aromatic cross-conjugated oligomers based on the azulene building block, we have discovered a rare set of molecules composed of a central oligoquinane moiety (oligoquinane structures are uncommon) in which a carbazole unit is incorporated at the 2-azulene position. Some of these molecules strikingly exhibit anti-Kasha

phosphorescent emission, which is an unprecedented phenomenon for a hydrocarbon pure heavy-atom-free organic molecule. While at room temperature only anti-Kasha fluorescence persists, at cryogenic conditions (80 K) both anti-Kasha fluorescence and phosphorescence clearly coexist. Upon enlarging the oligoquinane structure, the anti-Kasha phosphorescence blurs out due to the decreasing role of the carbazole unit to the relevant optical excitations. These findings, in our opinion, represent a breakthrough and open the way to further investigation of improved molecules with this basic azulene-oligoquinane/carbazole composition for photonic applications. Also, this study provides fundamental insights into the mechanisms of anti-Kasha processes, which can be taken into account to expand the possibilities for these excited states to produce new processes aside of energy dissipation (Kasha rule, internal conversion) or light emission (anti-Kasha fluorescence and phosphorescence).

Declarations

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Author contributions

M.D.-F. did theoretical calculations and all spectroscopic measurements. J.M.M.-B. contributed with the interpretation of the transient absorption measurements and to the writing of the article. C.W. and J.L. synthesized the compounds and characterized their structures. A.O. D.C. performed electronic structure calculations and analyzed and rationalized the obtained results. J.L., D.C, and J.C. conceived the work, directed the spectroscopic part and co-wrote the article.

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Schemes

Schemes 1 and 2 are available in the Supplementary Files section.

Figures

Figure 1

X-Ray Solid State Characterization. **a,b**, Single crystal structures of **NB2A1** (**a**) and **NB0A3** (**b**) with ellipsoids at the 30% probability level. **c**, Analysis on the modular self-assembly of **NB2A1** into a porous framework with 1D channels. **d**, Molecular stackings of **NB0A3**.

Figure 2

Experimental and Calculated Steady State Absorption Spectra. **a**, Absorption spectra of **NB2A1** at 298 (purple line) and 80 K (pink line) (top) and their TDDFT vertical transitions (purple bars) together with their oscillator strengths (f) values (bottom). **b**, Table with TDDFT theoretical and experimental values for **NB2A1** and their composition as one-electron interorbital transitions. **c**, Orbital topologies for the three molecules. Dashed lines assist to identify those orbitals with similar contributions on the azulene unit. All calculations were done at the CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory. H=HOMO: highest occupied molecular orbital; L=LUMO: lowest unoccupied molecular orbital.

Figure 3

Photophysical Characterization. **a,b,c**, Absorption (solid lines), emission (shaded lines) and excitation (broken lines with color corresponding to their associated emissions) spectra of **NB2A1** (**a**), **NB0A1** (**b**) and **NB0A3** (**c**) at 298 (top) and 80 K (bottom). Insets correspond to the **NB2A1** emission decay of the two 347 and 422 nm emission bands at 80 K and at 353 nm at 298 K. **d**, Femtosecond transient absorption spectra of **NB2A1** in 2-MeTHF at 298 K obtained at representative delay times. **e**, Vertical zoom of panel **d** to better depict the spectra up to 1 ns compared with the normalized microsecond transient absorption spectrum obtained at 1 μ s (squares). **f**, Femtosecond transient absorption spectra of **NB0A3** in 2-MeTHF at 298 K obtained at representative delay times. Femtosecond transient absorption data has been obtained at a power of 0.25 mW exciting at 300 and 450 nm, for **NB2A1** and **NB0A3**, respectively. Microsecond transient absorption data has been obtained exciting at 355 nm with an excitation density energy of 80 μ J cm^{-2} .

Figure 4

Photophysical Dynamics. Jablonski diagram for **NB2A1** indicating the anti-Kasha fluorescence and anti-Kasha phosphorescence emissions as well as the main channels of intersystem crossing and internal conversion. Molecular orbitals describing the main contribution to the S₅@S₀ de-excitation at the S₅ optimized geometry and T₄@S₀ de-excitation at the T₄ optimized geometry of **NB2A1** computed at the CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level. Values for each individual ISC channel are provided as **DE/SOCC** where **DE** is the singlet-triplet vertical excitation energies ($DE = E(S_n) - E(T_m)$ in meV) and **SOCCs** (in cm⁻¹) between excited singlet and close-lying triplet states computed at respective excited singlet optimized geometries at the CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level. Vertical solid lines represent photon emissions; ISC channels are represented as horizontal broken lines (main ISC channels -large SOCC and small DE - are given as pink arrows); and wavy arrows represent internal conversion/vibrational relaxation.

Supplementary Files

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- [SupportingInformationFile.docx](#)

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